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Influence Of Record Keeping On Principals' Administrative Effectiveness In public Secondary Schools In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined influence of record keeping on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Descriptive research design was used for this study. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of this study comprised 267 principals in the public secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Anambra State and the entire population was used for this study. The instruments for data collection were two sets of questionnaires structured by the researcher tagged; "Record Keeping Questionnaire (RKQ)" and "Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ)". The face validity of the instruments was established by three experts. The construct validity of the instruments was established using Principal Component Analysis approach. Cronbach Alpha procedure was used to determine the internal consistency of the instruments. The collected data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and paired t-test to test hypotheses. The findings of this study indicated that record creation, record storage, and record retrieval have significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It was recommended Principals should appoint an experienced teacher to help ensure that adequate records are created from reports, minutes, personnel records, students' data, administrative decisions, notices and other correspondences manually or in an electronic form for immediate and future use in the school. Principals should ensure that created records are protected from loss or damage by making sure that they are stored manually in papers, files, drawers, shelves, safe rooms or electronically through the use of electronic devices such as computers, CD Roms, flash drives, and clouds.

Keywords: Record Keeping, Principals, Administrative Effectiveness.

INTRODUCTION

Secondary education is a very important level of the Nigerian education system. This level of education acts as a bridge between the primary and tertiary institutions of learning. It is presumed to lay a solid foundation which shapes the present and future development of learners. Public secondary schools are owned and managed by the government with principals as head. Principals' are responsible for handling all the administrative roles in schools. The administrative functions principals are expected to perform include: planning, organizing, supervising, staffing, evaluating, coordinating, leadership, purchasing and

maintenance of instructional materials, equipment and facilities, management of school finance, maintaining of discipline, supervision of instruction. Principals are expected to perform these administrative roles effectively. Principals' administrative effectiveness is pivotal for school success. Principals' administrative effectiveness is a major component for achieving the goals of education at the secondary school level (Oraegbunam et al. 2025). In other words, the success and failure of secondary school depends largely on principals' administrative effectiveness.

Principals' administrative effectiveness is the ability of school principals to handle the day-to-day affairs of secondary schools where they work effectively. Adegun cited in Ejimofor (2022) opined that principals' administrative effectiveness is their ability to apply innovative, organizational and management strategies and make the most efficient use of resources which is not only money but also time and expertise in their schools in order to realize set school goals. It is their capability to harness available resources in the school to achieve pre-determined goals. It is their ability to utilize the human and material resources in the school effectively to achieve productivity. Principals' administrative effectiveness is the outcome of their operations, correspondences, and activities of the organization. Uche cited in Babalola et al. (2021) stressed that principals' administrative effectiveness is a symbol of good administrative style which is visible in team work, high morale, motivated staff, quality teaching and conducive school environment which helps to improve school performance as well as ensuring that students acquire knowledge, skills, values and habits that empower them to contribute positively to the society.

Unfortunately, in Anambra State public secondary schools, some principals' administrative ineffectiveness from personal observation of the researcher has become a matter of concern. The administrative functions of principals involves the proper utilization of human and material resources and these include maintaining students and staff discipline, supervision of instruction, management of school facilities, maintaining school and community relationship (Ohamobi & Anasiudu, 2024). These crucial functions of principals seem neglected in some public secondary schools in Anambra State. Some principals spend more time in the office attending to visitors, answering phone calls, dishing out instructions to staff. Sometimes they stay out of office for weeks attending meetings leaving their administrative functions unattended to. This has affected teachers and students negatively.

Principals' administrative ineffectiveness is evidenced through their poor supervision of instruction, improper decision making, poor motivation of teachers and students, poor communication in the school, indiscipline in the school, social vices among students, non-utilization of instructional materials during instruction delivery and so on. Principals' administrative effectiveness is important in educational institutions where the primary objective is human capacity development, since education is considered the vehicle to develop intellect for creativity and to teach values and tolerance that promote economic, social, cultural and political development of nations and individual (Ayushi (2018). Principals are expected to perform their administrative functions effectively and show proper accountability through record keeping. In other words, an important aspect of principals' administrative functions is record keeping. In line with Musembe (2016) who pointed out that one of the ways of judging principals' effectiveness is through their record keeping.

Record keeping is the process of generating and storing information about an organization. Record keeping is the act of creating and maintaining records in organizations such as schools, banks, hospitals and other service and non-service organizations (Amie-Ogan & Tagbo, 2021). Record keeping shows an evidence for a fact or an occurrence which could be in written or in other permanent forms for immediate or future use. Many students and staff academic activities, school facilities and other important administrative programmes needs to be taken care of accurately for the smooth running of the school as the 21st century system of school management is mainly on accurate record (Manafa et al., 2022) Record keeping constitutes what could be described as the life wire of an organization. Otu cited in Elujekwute et al. (2021) defined record keeping as a written account of facts, events and activities set down in a book of reference or preserved for future use. Every organization depends so much upon record keeping for their sustained existence and development. Record keeping is very

important in school administration because it affects all other aspects of school administration such as planning, budgeting, staffing, facilities, discipline and so on (Alabi, 2017). Record keeping helps in keeping track of information and without it, it may be difficult to ascertain progress, take decisions or plan for the future. The maintenance of the trend in the history of teaching and learning process could be aided through record keeping.

There are a lot of records that need to be kept in the school for the achievement of school goals. It is through record keeping that principals as administrators of secondary schools will be able to ascertain the quantity of school plants and equipment, their condition, the number of student enrolment, the number that graduated, vital information about staff and students. In other words, there are various types of records to be kept in the school. Obi and Manafa (2020) asserted that important records to be kept in every school include: the school calendar, log book, admission register, students' attendance register, teachers' attendance register/biometric log in and log out machine, cash book, stock register of equipment, education laws, national policy on education, vote book, annual report, scheme of work, syllabus, lesson plan, lesson note, school time table, continuous assessment dossier, punishment book, visitor's book, inspection report file, staff movement book, record of work, staff class attendance register, staff confidential report, testimonial/transfer certificate booklet, duty book, official correspondence file, school budget, school impress book and minute books. All school records can be categorized into statutory and non-statutory records. Statutory records are compulsory records required by government to be kept in school and provided on demand to government officials. They are records in relation to adherence to government statues or laws and are often inspected or audited by concerned government authorities. Non-statutory records in the school are records kept and maintained by schools voluntarily because of the vital information they provide for the smooth running of the day-day activities of the school. The success and failure of any organization is dependent on record keeping (Amie-Ogan & Tagbo, 2021). The important of record keeping cannot be over emphasized as it forms the basis for all school activities.

The basis of record keeping is the efficient creation and handling of records (both paper and electronic) throughout their life-cycle, from creation to disposal (Seniwoliba et al., 2017). Personal experience of the researcher showed that there a lot of difficulties faced by staff and students in some public secondary schools in Anambra State as a result of inappropriate record keeping. Some schools work with incomplete or inaccurate records because the school cannot lay their hands on the original and correct records. Sometimes, lack of adequate record keeping causes delay for the issuing of some important documents to staff and students who are still in the school or to those who have already graduated. Some students have missed examinations, some have spent time and money in swearing affidavit due to wrong information from their school and some teachers have also missed their promotion due to misplacement of their files. Record keeping in the school is important to both staff and students. Records kept in the school serve as reference point when information is needed in the school. Records serve as a basis for review, study and evaluation of all happenings in the school. Adeyemi cited in Elujekwute et al. (2021) maintained that record keeping connotes all activities concerned with the creation, storage, retrieval, retention and deposition of all information relating to what goes on in the school, who is in the school, the school plant as well as other information pertinent to the growth of the schools. Record keeping involves generating, storing, updating, retrieval and destruction of information (Sabitu, 2022). Record keeping includes all activities involving record creation, record receipt, record maintenance, record usage, record storage and record disposal (Babalola et al., 2021). This study examined record creation, record storage, and record retrieval.

Record creation is the process of producing original data from scratch. Babalola et al. (2021) defined record creation as the documentation of information and organizational activities. It is the originating of information from the primary or secondary source. The opening of folders or files for personnel or activities in an organization is record creation Onunwor (2022). There are different activities that take place in schools on daily basis and it is through record creation that the evidence of such activities or data is gotten for immediate or later use. Record creation include: documenting correspondences from reliable

sources, verifying the accuracy of information before documenting it, complying to the order from higher authorities regarding documentation of relevant information and documenting information that is backed up with original documents where necessary (Jonathan & Nwankwo 2020). It is important for records to be created accurately because it is the data from the record created that an organization will work with. Records can be created from different sources. Owan et al. (2019) stressed that records are created from reports, minutes, personnel records, administrative decisions, notices and other correspondences. Records can be created manually or in an electronic form. It is important the records created be stored appropriately.

Record storage is the process of safeguarding the created records for future use. It involves protecting acquired information from loss or damage. Luyombya and Ndagire (2020) defined record storage as the process of protecting records against both environmental and human interferences so that the information they carry is secure. Record storage involves keeping records to ensure that their integrity is preserved. It involves protecting information or records from damage or theft. Malake and Phiri (2020) asserted that record storage is safeguarding records from unauthorized access so that they will be available in case of queries or other referrals. Any record created can either be secured manually or electronically. Records can be stored manually in papers, files, drawers, shelves and in safe rooms. Records can be stored electronically through the use of electronic devices such as computers, CD Roms, flash drives, etcetera (Amie-Ogan & Tagbo, 2021). They can also be stores in clouds. Cloud storage is the method of keeping records online through a cloud computing service provider who manages the record keeping but the aid of internet connection (Samman & Smug 2021). Record storage is vital in all organizations because every record has its own special importance and value to the success of the organization. There is need for stored records to be properly stored for easy retrieval.

Record retrieval is the process of getting stored records for use from where they are stored. It involves locating and obtaining stored records for use. Onweh et al. (2018) opined that record retrieval is the process of obtaining data from their storage as at when they are needed by administrators. A record that cannot be located by a user when needed is as good as a record that does not exist. Hence, it is necessary that records in the school should be stored in such a way that they remain reliable and easy to retrieve and in a timely manner in order to meet the need of the user. Malake and Phiri (2020) pointed out that records stored either manually or electronically should be easy to locate, retrieved in a reliable state and timely so as to serve the needs for which it is meant for. Searching for records that are not properly stored for easy retrieval can be time consuming for the person searching for it and the user. School records need to be easily assessable for easy retrieval because of their usefulness (Koko & Nwiyi, 2019). Records are retrieved for use, after which they may be retained or disposed.

It is the duty of principals as heads in secondary schools to handle records from their creation stage through their disposal stage. Record keeping is an integral component of every organization because it helps to ensure the timely flow of reliable and needed information within and outside the organization. Thus, in spite of the great benefits of record keeping in the realization of educational goals, it seems that record keeping system in many public secondary schools in Anambra State is still being paid lip service, not minding that lack of proper records will result to loss of vital information which might affect either the students, staff or the school as an organization. Many students have experienced series of challenges in school due to lack of proper record keeping such as: misspelling of names, interchanging of test and examination scores, printing of wrong information on certificates and so on. Proper record keeping could be a measure of principals' administrative effectiveness.

It is worrisome to note that some principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State seem to show ineffectiveness in discharging their duties. The functions principals are supposed to perform include, students' discipline, supervision of instruction, management of school facilities, maintaining school and community relationship, but some principals spend more of their time in the office attending to visitors, answering phone calls, dishing out instructions to staff. Sometimes they stay out of office for weeks attending meetings leaving their administrative functions unattended to. Lack of principals' administrative effectiveness could be detrimental to families, school and the society in general. It is based on this

background that the researcher intends to examine the influence of record keeping on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the problem

Principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State is a germane for the achievement of the goals of secondary education which is beneficial for the development of the society. Personal observation by the researcher as a teacher who have worked in some public secondary schools in Anambra State showed that some principals stay almost all day in their office either attending to visitors, spending so more time in making and answering calls with their mobile phones, some principals hardly stay in the school, it is either they are attending one meeting or the other, some teacher come to school and some leave before close of work without being disciplined. Some principals do not even have time to supervise the quality of instructions teachers deliver. Some students and parents stand long hours waiting for one information or the other concerning their data which they submitted earlier to the school and leave disappointed.

This is worrisome because the importance of secondary education is well known to Anambra State government and that is why efforts are being increased to ensure that the best is given to students so that they will equally give out the best to the society. If principals' continue to exhibit poor attitude in their administrative duties, it will be difficult to achieve the pre-determined education goals at the secondary school level. Both the academic and non-academic staff will be left to perform their duty the way they like and the quality of leaning outcome will decrease. The general society will be affected negatively. A lot of factor could cause principals' administrative ineffectiveness. They include; work overload, inadequate educational facilities, lack of adequate number of experienced teachers, stress, unavailability of required information, lack of good record keeping, and so on. It is based on this premise that this study examined the influence of record keeping on principals' administrative effectiveness in the areas of record creation, record storage, record updating, record retrieval and record in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the influence of record keeping on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the extent record creation influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. examine the extent record storage influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. ascertain the extent record retrieval influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does record creation influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. To what extent does record storage influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. To what extent does record retrieval influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Record creation has no significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Record storage has no significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State..

3. Record retrieval has no significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

METHOD

The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of this study consisted of 267 principals in the public secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Anambra State. Census sampling was adopted because the entire population was used for the study. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study tested at 0.05 level of significant. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Two structured instruments by the researcher was used for data collection in this study. The first instrument was tagged "Record Keeping Questionnaire (RKQ)". This instrument was used to elicit information from the respondents on record keeping. This instrument was made up of two sections named A and B. Section A contained the personal information of the respondents. Section B contained items on record keeping arranged in three clusters named clusters A-C. Cluster A contained 10 items on record creation, Cluster B contained 10 items on record storage, and Cluster C contained 10 items on record retrieval. The items are placed on a 4-point scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE). The range of scores were weighted as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The second instrument was tagged "Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ)". This instrument was used to elicit information from the respondents on administrative effectiveness. It contained 20 items on principals' administrative effectiveness. The items are placed on a 4-point scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE). The range of scores were weighted as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The face validity of the instruments was established by three experts. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) approach was used to explore the construct validity of the instruments and The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value used as a measure of sampling adequacy was obtained for the two instruments: Record Keeping and Principals' Administrative Effectiveness was 0.777. The higher value of the result which is greater than 0.500 indicated that the sample of the study was large enough to perform PCA. The Cronbach Alpha procedure was used to determine the internal consistency of the instruments. The average reliability coefficient for the two instruments showed a value of 0.751 and the instruments were considered reliable for this study.

Five research assistants helped the researcher to administer and retrieve the instruments. On-the-spot completion and retrieving method was used to administer and collect the instruments. This method helped to ensure that the return rate of the instruments was high. The copies of the instruments filled and successfully retrieved from the respondents were used for data analysis. Out of 267 instruments distributed, 256 was successfully retrieved (95.88% return rate) while 4.12% could not be retrieved despite several attempts made. The data collected after the administration of the instrument was analyzed. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and paired t-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. For decision on the research questions, any item with 2.50 and above was accepted while any item with 2.49 and below was not accepted. All analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 27.

RESULTS

The data gotten from the respondents were used for analysis and the result obtained were presented in line with the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Questions 1: *To what extent does record creation influence principals’ administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation (SD) of the extent record creation influence principals’ administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT: In my school:	N	Mean	SD	Remark
1	digital format is used for record creation to prevent unauthorized access	256	2.39	1.06	LE
2	records creation is sometimes paper based because it is required by the regulating body for auditing	256	2.83	0.89	HE
3	records are created from emails for communication with parents	256	2.20	0.58	LE
4	written reports are source of record creation because they provide permanent documentation	256	3.16	0.89	HE
5	all incoming records are registered in order to use them to create records	256	1.66	1.24	LE
6	all records are assigned date accurately for effective creation of records	256	2.40	0.81	LE
7	records received from reliable source are recorded with appropriate titles for easy retrieval	256	2.99	1.00	HE
8	information from new students is used to create their admission records for easy verification of their identity	256	3.16	0.68	HE
9	photocopy of records are kept for creation of record in case of loss of the original copy	256	1.79	0.96	LE
10	records are created from updated documents for monitoring of students’ academic progress	256	2.50	0.96	HE
Mean of means			2.50		HE

Table 1 showed the extent to which record creation influenced principals’ administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The table showed that items 1, 3, 5, 6 and 7 with mean of 2.39, 2.20, 1.66, 2.40, and 1.79 respectively showed that record creation influenced principals’ administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a low extent. The table also showed that items 2, 4, 7, 8, 10 with means of 2.83, 3.16, 2.99, 3.16, and 2.50 respectively showed that record creation influenced principals’ administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent. Invariably, the mean of means of the extent to which record creation influenced principals’ administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State was 2.50 indicating to a high extent. This showed that record creation influenced principals’ administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent.

Research Questions 2: *To what extent does record storage influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation (SD) of the extent record storage influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT – In my school:	N	Mean	SD	Remark
11	wood cabinets are used for storing various records because of its durability	256	2.83	1.06	HE
12	steel cabinets are provided for storage of files to ensure that they are protected from fire damage	256	2.18	0.74	LE
13	authorized personnel only are in charge of storing records for effective management	256	2.20	0.91	LE
14	records are stored according to their type in order to reduce time spent on searching for them	256	2.40	1.10	LE
15	some records are stored in compact disc because of its portability	256	1.16	0.69	VLE
16	google cloud is one of the storage places for records because it facilitates information sharing	256	1.71	0.68	VLE
17	there is a particular room for storing records that are confidential to prevent unauthorized access	256	2.69	0.95	HE
18	all stored records have duplicate to provide backup in case of loss of the original	256	2.18	1.11	LE
19	all records are indexed for easy retrieval	256	1.51	0.89	VLE
20	records are organized alphabetically when storing for easy retrieval	256	1.33	0.74	VLE
Mean of means			2.03		LE

Table 2 revealed the extent to which record storage influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The table revealed that items 12, 13, 14, and 18 with mean of 2.18, 2.20, 2.40, and 2.18 respectively showed that record storage influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a low extent. The table also showed that items 11 and 17 with means of 2.83 and 2.69 respectively showed that record storage influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent while items 15, 16, 19 and 20 with means of 1.16, 1.71, 1.51 and 1.33 revealed that record storage influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a very high extent. Also, the mean of means of the extent to which record storage influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State was 2.03 indicating to a low extent. Hence, record storage influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a low extent.

Research Questions 3: *To what extent does record retrieval influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation (SD) of the extent record retrieval influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT – In my school:	N	Mean	SD	Remark
31	files are removed from wood cabinets only when they are needed for use to safeguard the documents	256	2.73	0.74	HE
32	only authorized staff have access to retrieve records in order to maintain file integrity	256	3.20	0.47	HE
33	records are arranged in alphabetical order so that they can be retrieved easily	256	2.32	0.89	LE
34	some records are only accessible electronically to ensure that sensitive information are guarded	256	2.20	1.37	LE
35	passwords are used to protect digital records to ensure access control	256	1.18	0.68	VLE
36	records are retrieved on request to provide evidence of payment of school fees for proper decision-making	256	3.12	0.81	HE
37	records requested by external parties always follow specific procedure to ensure that they are handled by designated staff	256	3.39	1.15	HE
38	records can be retrieved manually to verify accuracy of information for effective administration	256	2.66	1.18	HE
39	records are assigned file names for easy retrieval	256	3.06	1.07	HE
40	proper list of all stored records are kept by authorized staff for easy retrieval of records	256	1.16	0.68	VLE
Mean of means			2.51		HE

Table 3 portrayed the extent to which record retrieval influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Items 35 and 40 with mean of 1.18 and 1.16 respectively showed that record retrieval influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a very low extent. Items 33 and 34 with means of 2.32 and 2.20 respectively showed that record retrieval influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a low extent while items 31, 32, 35, 37, 38 and 39 with means of 2.73, 3.20, 3.12, 3.39, 2.66 and 3.06 indicated that record retrieval influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent. Meanwhile, the mean of means was 2.51 showing that record retrieval influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent.

Test of Hypotheses

In order to make decision on the extent record keeping influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State, the following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Record creation has no significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Paired sample t-test of the extent record creation influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value	Decision
Record creation	256	28.83	3.56	76.29	255	0.001	
principals' administrative effectiveness	256	59.95	5.82				Significant

Table 4 showed the paired sample t-test of the influence of record creation on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The table showed a paired sample t-test of 76.29 with 255 degrees of freedom and associated p-value of 0.001. The associated p-value of 0.001 was less than 0.05 level of significance, therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is a significant influence of record creation on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2

Record storage has no significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Paired sample t-test of the extent record storage influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value	Decision
Record creation	256	39.02	2.77	74.67	255	0.003	
principals' administrative effectiveness	256	59.95	5.82				Significant

Table 5 revealed the paired sample t-test of the influence of record storage on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The table showed a paired sample t-test of 74.67 with 255 degrees of freedom and associated p-value of 0.003 which was less than 0.05 level of significance. This showed that there is a significant influence of record storage on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that record storage has no significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State was rejected.

Hypothesis 3

Record retrieval has no significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Paired sample t-test of the extent record retrieval influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value	Decision
Record creation	256	30.00	5.35	60.45	255	0.041	
principals' administrative effectiveness	256	59.95	5.82				Significant

Result in Table 6 showed the paired sample t-test of the influence of record retrieval on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The paired sample t-test was 60.45. The degree of freedom was 255 and p-value of 0.002 was obtained. The p-value of 0.002 was less than 0.05 level of significance. Invariably, record retrieval has significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that record retrieval has no significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings was presented in accordance with the results from the research questions and hypotheses as follows:

The extent record creation influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The finding of this study showed that record creation influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent. The study also revealed that record creation has a significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding agreed with that of Mureebe and Lwanga (2023) which revealed that records creation to a high extent positively and significantly influenced principals' administrative effectiveness. The agreement between the two findings could be because of the closeness of the period when they were carried out. Record creation which is originating of information from the primary or secondary source is very important in school it is through record creation that data is gotten for school administration by principals. If records are not created accurately, principals might end up working with inaccurate data. Hence the need for proper record creation as it influences principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The extent record storage influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Record storage influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a low extent. There is a significant influence of record creation on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is in line with that of Amie-Ogan and Tagbo (2021) which maintained that record storage is one of the record keeping practices which significant with and enhances principals' administrative effectiveness. Despite the fact that the studies were carried out in different geographical locations, (Rivers State and Anambra State), there is still agreement between them probably because the time span between the two studies is not too far.

The result of this study also agreed with the findings of Ossai (2024) which revealed that record storage influenced principals' administrative effectiveness. The agreement between the two studies could be because the two studies were carried out in secondary schools and the period when the two research were carried out was close. There is need for safeguarding created records in public secondary schools in Anambra State for future use because every record has its own special importance and value to the success of the school as an organization.

The extent record retrieval influence principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The study revealed that record retrieval influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent. Findings from the study also showed that record retrieval has significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding supports the findings of Umar and Halilu (2023) which showed that record retrieval influence the principals' administrative effectiveness. The research was conducted in Bichi Education Zone of Kano State and yet the findings agreed with the present study maybe because the two studies were conducted in a secondary school. It could also be due to the nearness of the time when the two studies were carried out. Principals need to ensure that school records should be easy to retrieve and in a timely manner in order to meet the need of the user because a relevant record that cannot be located by a user when needed is as good as a record that does not exist. Searching for records that are not properly stored for easy retrieval can be time consuming for the person searching for it and the user. Hence, the need for principals to ensure fast retrieval of records for effective administration

CONCLUSION

It was concluded based on the findings of this study that record creation and record retrieval influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent and

they have significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Record storage influenced principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a low extent and it has significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. In conclusion, record creation, record storage, and record retrieval have significant influence on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were proffered based on the result of this study;

1. Principals should appoint an experienced teacher to help ensure that adequate records are created from reports, minutes, personnel records, students' data, administrative decisions, notices and other correspondences manually or in an electronic form for immediate and future use in the school.
2. Principals should ensure that created records are protected from loss or damage by making sure that they are stored manually in papers, files, drawers, shelves, safe rooms or electronically through the use of electronic devices such as computers, CD Roms, flash drives, and clouds.
3. Principals should that stored paper files are tagged accordingly and all electronic files given adequate file names and kept in relevant folders for easy retrieval.

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